

HOW PRO-GAZA PROTESTS ARE RAISING QUESTIONS ABOUT THE VALUES IN UNIVERSITIES RANKING?

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ABSTRACT

Pro-Gaza protests at universities are raising significant questions about the Academic Institutions' values and ranking criteria worldwide. The nature and concentration of these protests, particularly at elite universities, show the importance of elite students in creating a human wakeup. Further empathy calls for human rights protection and development. Therefore, this raises the need for another measure for universities ranking in relevance to student freedom of speech and academic freedom.

The universities' negative reaction to pro-Gaza protests has underscored significant questions about these institutional values, student activism's role, and student bodies' socioeconomic composition. The authors of this paper believe that these events are prompting the need for a re-evaluation of how universities' rankings are perceived, particularly concerning their commitments to free speech, diversity, and social justice.

By incorporating measures of academic freedom, student engagement, and support for political causes such as FreePalestine, the paper advocates for a more holistic assessment of universities and calls for an approach that ensures institutions are evaluated not only for academic excellence but also for their commitment to social justice, ethical standards, and fostering meaningful societal engagement.

The paper proposes new criteria for giving students a chance to protect the students and the academic staff who call for freedom protests in issues similar to FreePalestine and stop the genocide in Gaza. This research should open the door for further research in this line that would calibrate universities' ranking based on their stand on human development and freedom.

Keywords: Universities Ranking, War on Gaza, Pro-Palestine Protests, Students Academic Freedom

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1. INTRODUCTION

Pro-Gaza protests have predominantly occurred at highly selective universities with lower percentages of students from lower-income backgrounds. Institutions like Columbia, Harvard, and MIT have seen significant protest activities, including encampments and large-scale demonstrations. In contrast, universities with higher proportions of Pell Grant recipients and working-class students, such as many public universities and historically Black colleges and universities (HBCUs), have experienced fewer protests. This disparity raises questions about student activism's social and economic demographics and whether elite institutions inherently foster more politically active environments. Buheji et al. (2024a)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. How Gaza is Reviving the History of Students Activism in Campuses

The Pro-Gaza and Pro-FreePalestine protests have prompted universities to grapple with their values, particularly around free speech and political activism. There is a tension between maintaining campus order and upholding students' rights to protest. For instance, Columbia University faced backlash for involving the NYPD in managing protests, which some viewed as an infringement on free speech. This response has led to debates on whether university actions align with their stated commitments to free expression and social justice. Buheji et al. (2024a)

Many of the universities involved in the current protests have a long history of student activism. Institutions like Georgetown and Loyola Marymount have seen significant student-led movements in the past, such as during the Civil Rights era and anti-apartheid protests. This historical context suggests that these universities have been traditional grounds for vocal student activism, which continues today in the context of the Gaza conflict.

The Pro-Palestine protests have also brought to light issues of diversity and inclusion within universities. While elite institutions may have fewer lower-income students, the diverse backgrounds of protesters reflect broader concerns about global injustices and solidarity. This raises questions about how universities support and engage with students from various socioeconomic backgrounds and whether their policies and values truly reflect inclusive principles.

2.2. Understanding the Students' Generation Demand and Empathetic Mindset

It is not by coincidence that the world will experience a surge in university student protests if we understand the unique characteristics and perspectives of the Generation Z cohort. As the oldest members of this generation arrived on college campuses in 2013, educators have had to adapt their approaches to recruit, educate, and graduate these students effectively. Generation Z, also known as the "digital natives," has been shaped by a context vastly different from their predecessors. As explored in one study, the behavioural and attitudinal changes observed in Generation Z engineering students provide valuable insights into this demographic (Dhinakaran et al., 2020).

Compared to previous generations, Generation Z has grown up in a world marked by technological advancements, economic instability, and heightened safety concerns (Dhinakaran et al., 2020). This has resulted in a generation that is not only technologically savvy, collaborative, and demanding of active participation in their learning environments, but even empathetic about fairness, equality, and freedom of choices, Buheji et al. (2024b), Goldbach and Hamza-Lup (2020). This generation's reliance on technology and online platforms has also contributed to their engagement in social and political issues, as they seek to make their voices heard in the digital realm. This generation does not believe in the mainstream media and would try to get news from a trusted source. In the case of Gaza, this Generation is getting its news directly from the field and the victims. Buheji (2024a), Buheji (2024b).

2.3. Evaluating the Universities Administrative Responses vs. Academic Freedom in Cases of Pro-Palestine Protests

Universities' responses to the protests have varied, with some taking more restrictive measures that have sparked criticism from both students and faculty. Actions such as suspensions, arrests, and cancellations of graduation events at institutions like USC and Columbia have been seen as undermining academic freedom and student rights. This situation challenges universities to balance security concerns with their commitment to academic freedom and open discourse. Buheji and Hasan (2024), Tiede (2018)

Normally, high-ranking university graduate leaders bring changes to their organisations, communities, countries, and even the world. Therefore, the graduating students should be expected to try to practice this role earlier when they express their opinions via protesters during their studies, even if it will cost them to lose their place in the University. The notion that leading high-rank universities are inclined to position themselves as leaders in sociopolitical discourse is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that warrants careful examination.

While it is true that prestigious universities often leverage their influence to express opinions on various issues, the reasons behind this tendency and its implications are not always straightforward. One perspective suggests that universities, particularly those with a strong reputation and resources, may view their role as opinion leaders as a means of shaping the broader sociopolitical landscape (Filho et al., 2019).

This notion is supported by the observation that the prestige and competitive advantages of elite universities are often reflected in their ability to attract high-caliber students and faculty and secure significant funding and resources (Abramo et al., 2012). Governments and policymakers may have a vested interest in cultivating and supporting these "champion institutions" due to the potential social and economic benefits they can provide to the nation and local region (Public Research Universities: Serving the Public Good, 2015). In this context, universities may feel compelled to engage in sociopolitical discourse actively, even if it means risking their place within the academic hierarchy, in an effort to exercise their influence and shape the public narrative. However, this approach is not without its critics. Some scholars have argued that the shifting power dynamics within higher education, with increasing emphasis on individual choice, market-based principles, and state actors' interests, may undermine universities' traditional autonomy and academic freedom. Buheji and Hasan (2024), Leal et al. (2019), Tiede (2018).

2.4. Evaluating the Necessity of Police Intervention in Universities Campuses to Suppress Pro-Palestine Student Protesters

The role of police in university student protests and its impact on university rankings is a topic that has sparked widespread debate and discussions in academic and social circles. As universities continue to grapple with the challenges of student activism and protests, the way in which law enforcement agencies handle these situations can have significant repercussions on a university's reputation and standing in national and international rankings. This paper aims to examine the dynamics at play when police intervene in student protests and explore the potential influence on a university's academic and social standing. By delving into this complex issue, we can better understand the broader implications for universities and their relationships with law enforcement bodies. Anderson (2015)

While some argue that police intervention in university student protests is necessary to maintain order and ensure students' safety, others believe such intervention can have detrimental effects on the academic environment and the university's reputation. However, suppose one goes deeper, especially in the 2024 Pro-Palestine student. In that case, they are asking their universities to be more transparent about their relation with Israel and then to plan to boycott, or disinvest from the investment with Israeli-related entities, Buheji, M and Ahmed, D (2023).

Proponents of police intervention argue that it is the responsibility of law enforcement to uphold the law and prevent disruptions to academic activities. They assert that without police intervention, student protests could escalate into violent confrontations, leading to property damage and endangering the safety of students and faculty. Additionally, proponents argue that universities must maintain a peaceful and conducive learning environment, and police intervention is crucial in upholding this environment, Buheji (2020). They contend that universities should not be held responsible for the actions of individual students who choose to engage in disruptive protests, and that law enforcement agencies are necessary to enforce discipline and order.

Moreover, proponents argue that a university's rankings and reputation should not be heavily influenced by law enforcement actions during student protests. They assert rankings should focus solely on academic excellence, research contributions, and faculty qualifications, rather than external factors such as police intervention in student protests (Blinder, 2023). Overall, proponents of police intervention in university student protests believe that it is necessary to ensure the academic community's safety and security. Anderson (2015)

The role of police in managing student protesters on university campuses has been a topic of concern and debate (On Campus Police Forces, 2021). Some argue that the police should maintain a presence on campus to ensure the safety of students, staff, and property, as well as to enforce laws and maintain order (Anderson, 2015). Others, however, raise concerns about the potential for excessive use of force by police against peaceful protesters and the chilling effect it can have on freedom of expression and the right to peaceful assembly. Additionally, police involvement in handling student protesters can have significant implications for the relationship between universities and their students (Morgan, 2014). The police must strike a balance between maintaining security and respecting the rights of students to voice their opinions and engage in peaceful protests. Police Role in Universities student protesters. Anderson (2015)

2.5. Evaluating Freedom of Students Union in Pro-Palestine Protesters

Student unions have long played a vital role in advocating for students' rights and interests, particularly during widespread student protests and unrest. These organizations serve as a crucial interface between the student body and the university administration, providing a platform for students to voice their concerns and demands. (Altbach, 1996)

In the context of student protests, student unions can act as a stabilizing force, channelling the energy and passion of protesters into constructive and organized action. Research has shown that effective student unions are characterized by a strong sense of responsibility and commitment among their members. This helps maintain their legitimacy and influence, even as student priorities shift over time (Wu et al., 2020).

Student protests are often spontaneous in nature, arising from a range of fundamental concerns, such as dissatisfaction with university policies, perceived injustices, or broader sociopolitical issues. However, student unions can play a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of these protests, guiding them towards productive outcomes that address the root causes of student grievances, Luescher, and Türkoğlu (2022). The relationship between student unions and university leadership is complex, as the former often advocate for reforms that challenge the existing power structures and decision-making processes within the institution (Wickens, 2008).

2.6. The Scale for Universities Ranking vs. academic freedom in relevance to issues as Pro-Palestine Stand

As we speak today, the high rank universities are the universities which their student protesters for Gaza. Until now, the universities were ranked according to a variety of aspects such as Teaching, Citations, Research, International Outlook, and Industry Income, etc. Thus, from now on, new criteria will be added to the high-ranking universities, such as freedom of protestation, which reflects university engagement with society and students' way of critical thinking. Buheji and Hasan (2024)

As forbidding protestation against teaching values. This paper introduces this new scale for ranking universities and how these criteria give new measures for improvement. In the ever-evolving landscape of higher education, the criteria used to evaluate and rank universities have traditionally focused on metrics such as teaching quality, research output, international outlook, and industry engagement. However, as society grapples with pressing social and political issues, the need to incorporate a new measure of academic freedom and student engagement has become increasingly apparent. Buheji and Hasan (2024)

The traditional criteria for ranking universities have undoubtedly played a significant role in shaping the higher education landscape. However, as the global society grapples with social and political challenges, it has become increasingly evident that a new measure of academic freedom and student engagement is essential for a comprehensive evaluation of universities. Academic freedom and student engagement are crucial components that contribute to the overall ethos of a university. The ability of students to express their opinions freely and engage in meaningful discussions about critical social and political issues not only enriches their educational experience but also reflects the university's commitment to fostering a culture of open dialogue and critical thinking.

Furthermore, the inclusion of student activism as a measure for university rankings signifies a recognition of students' pivotal role in shaping the ethos and culture of the institutions they attend. By actively participating in protests and advocating for social and political change, students demonstrate their commitment to societal issues and their capacity for critical thinking, which are integral aspects of a well-rounded education.

As we delve deeper into the evolving landscape of university rankings, it becomes evident that embracing student activism and fostering engagement is crucial for universities to remain relevant and impactful in a rapidly changing world. Thus, the incorporation of student protest as a key metric for university rankings represents a necessary shift towards a more comprehensive and holistic evaluation of higher education institutions.

3. METHODOLOGY

This paper reviews the experience of ‘Pro-Palestine’ students protests on campuses across many elite universities around the Western world and the reaction of their universities. Therefore, this paper started with a comprehensive approach that ensures that universities are evaluated for their academic excellence and contributions to social justice and ethical standards. The authors target to create a shift in higher education institutions ranking criteria that will help foster an environment that supports free expression, critical thinking, and meaningful societal engagement, ultimately empowering students to advocate for important global issues.

The authors then go across the universities' ranking criteria's and select those that should include seeds that help universities advocate such freedom of expression activities even for sensitive issues as supporting the FreePalestine movement.

4. APPLICATION & ANALYSIS

4.1. Framework for A Value Based Academic Freedom Scale that takes Issues as FreePalestine into consideration

Incorporating academic freedom and the freedom to support political causes, such as supporting Gaza, into university ranking scales requires careful consideration of how these values are measured and reported. University ranking scales provide a more holistic assessment of institutions, highlighting their commitment to ethical standards, freedom of inquiry, and the overall quality of education. This approach ensures that rankings reflect not just academic excellence but also the broader impact and contributions of universities to society, including their support for political expression and advocacy in relevance to FreePalestine and similar other freedom movements. The following are the main constructs of the suggested scale.

4.2. Academic Freedom and Institutional Autonomy

4.2.1. Freedom of Inquiry

Evaluate the extent to which faculty and students can conduct research, teach, and express ideas without censorship or fear of repercussions. Take the issue of Pro-Palestine as an Example.

Indicators: Academic freedom policies, cases of censorship or interference, faculty surveys on freedom of inquiry.

4.2.2. Institutional Autonomy

Assess the degree of independence the university has from political, religious, or other external pressures. Take the issue of Pro-Palestine as an Example.

Indicators: Legal and structural autonomy, governance independence, external influence reports.

4.2.3. Tenure and Employment Practices

Consider policies on academic tenure and job security for faculty, ensuring protection from arbitrary dismissal. i.e. even for sensitive issues as taking stand for Gaza or Palestine.

Indicators: Tenure policies, employment protection laws, cases of academic dismissal.

4.3. Freedom to Support Political Causes (e.g., Gaza)

4.3.1. Support for Political Expression

Measure the university's policies and practices regarding the freedom of faculty and students to express support for political causes, such as Gaza.

Indicators: Existence of policies protecting political expression, incidents of repression or disciplinary action, student and faculty surveys on political expression.

4.3.2. Campus Climate for Activism

Assess the support and environment for political activism on campus. Take issue of Pro-Palestine as an Example.

Indicators: The number and variety of student organizations related to political causes, campus events, and activities supporting political causes, as well as administrative support or opposition.

4.4. Values and Ethical Standards

4.4.1. Code of Conduct

Examine the existence and enforcement of ethical codes for students, faculty, and staff.

Take issue of Pro-Palestine as an Example.

Indicators: Presence of a code of conduct, reporting and resolution mechanisms for violations.

4.4.2. Diversity and Inclusion:

Measure the university's commitment to promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion in its community. Take the issue of Pro-Palestine as an Example.

Indicators: Demographic diversity data, inclusion programs and initiatives, diversity training.

4.4.3. Sustainability Practices:

Evaluate the institution's efforts towards environmental sustainability and social responsibility. Take the issue of Pro-Palestine as an Example.

Indicators: Sustainability policies, green campus initiatives, community engagement in sustainability efforts.

4.5. Teaching and Learning Environment

4.5.1. Quality of Teaching

Include student evaluations, peer reviews, and teaching awards. Take the issue of teaching Palestinian rights, or the occupation of Palestine, as an Example.

Indicators: Student satisfaction surveys, teaching effectiveness reviews, professional development opportunities for faculty.

4.5.2. Student Support Services

Assess availability and quality of academic advising, mental health services, and career counselling, even for Pro-Palestine students.

Indicators: Student-to-advisor ratios, mental health service usage and satisfaction, career counselling success rates.

4.6. Graduate Outcomes and Employability

4.6.1. Employment Rates

Track the percentage of graduates employed in their field of study within a specific time frame after graduation without having their political stand as being Pro-Palestine affect them negatively.

Indicators: Graduate employment rates, job placement services, employer satisfaction surveys.

4.6.2. Alumni Success

Measure the achievements and positions held by alumni in various sectors regardless of their political stand.

Indicators: Alumni career progression, leadership roles held by alumni, alumni networks.

4.7. Student Experience and Satisfaction

4.7.1. Extracurricular Opportunities

Evaluate the range and quality of extracurricular activities, including clubs, sports, and arts, including the students stand for their political opinions.

Indicators: Number and variety of student organizations, participation rates, and support for extracurricular activities.

4.7.2. Governance and Administration

Transparent Governance Measure the transparency and inclusiveness of decision-making processes, even for sensitive issues as pro-Palestine.

Indicators: Governance structures, stakeholder participation in decision-making, transparency reports.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The analysis of Pro-Gaza protests across various universities highlights the significant role that institutional demographics and historical contexts play in shaping student activism, even in elite institutions like Columbia, Harvard, and MIT. Historical patterns of student activism, as seen in institutions like Georgetown and Loyola Marymount, reveal a long-standing tradition of vocal student engagement in sociopolitical issues. The current Pro-Palestine protests are a continuation of this legacy, bringing to light critical issues of diversity, inclusion, and the role of universities in supporting students from varied socioeconomic backgrounds. This raises the need for demand for reviewing universities' ranking and how it can give more academic freedom to students and faculty to support critical issues similar to FreePalestine and stopping the genocide on Gaza.

Universities' responses to these protests have varied, with some institutions taking restrictive measures that challenge academic freedom and student rights. The role of police intervention in managing protests further complicates the situation, raising concerns about the balance between maintaining order and respecting students' rights to free expression and peaceful assembly. The involvement of student unions in these protests highlights their crucial role in advocating for student interests and ensuring that protests lead to productive outcomes. Effective student unions can guide the energy of protests towards meaningful change, addressing the root causes of student grievances. The evolving criteria for university rankings now call for a more holistic approach that includes measures of academic freedom, student engagement, and the ability to support political causes. Incorporating these values into ranking scales will provide a comprehensive assessment of universities, reflecting their commitment to ethical standards and societal impact.

Therefore, there is a compelling need to redefine the criteria for university rankings to include measures of academic freedom, student engagement, and support for political causes. Incorporating these values into ranking scales will provide a more holistic assessment of universities, reflecting their commitment to ethical standards, societal impact, and the rights of students to support critical issues such as FreePalestine or stopping genocide in Gaza.

By embracing this comprehensive approach, we can ensure that universities are evaluated for their academic excellence and contributions to social justice and ethical standards. This shift in ranking criteria will help foster an environment that supports free expression, critical thinking, and meaningful societal engagement, ultimately empowering students to advocate for important global issues.

In conclusion, the Pro-Gaza protests have sparked a critical examination of student activism, university responses, and the broader implications for higher education institutions. By incorporating values of academic freedom and political engagement into university rankings, we can ensure that universities are evaluated for their academic excellence and contributions to social justice and ethical standards. This comprehensive approach will help universities foster an environment that supports free expression, critical thinking, and meaningful societal engagement.

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